

Knowledge Economy and Indigenous Experts: Indigenous Technical Knowledge (Itk) In Inland Aquaculture of West Bengal

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Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK) is an acquired knowledge of a local community that has been integrated through continued trial and error with locally available natural resources from the ambience around the community. Expertise in adoption and economic analyses of most ITKs have not been scientifically documented as their actual mechanism of action has seldom been investigated. In this direction, our study was conducted in three purposively selected districts viz. Malda, Bankura and Purba Medinipur with five developmental blocks each from the three districts. Twenty (20) farmers (respondents) from each of the five blocks in each selected district were selected through simple random sampling without replacement technique thereby comprising 300 farmers from the three districts (N=300) for collection of primary data.

Altogether fifty-nine (59) input based ITKs (Malda:19; Bankura:15; Purba Medinipur:25) were documented of which 20%, 53% and 64% ITKs were of recent origin; evolved during the last ten years in Bankura, Malda and Purba Medinipur district, respectively. Intra- and inter district variability was distinct towards approach and adoption of ITKs. The farmers of Malda were primarily concerned in adopting ITKs for environmental amelioration of the culture ponds; whereas, the farmers of Bankura and Purba Medinipur were more focussed in disease control, enhancement in carp seed production, disease management, environmental amelioration, growth promotion and feeding management of both carps and shrimps. In Malda district, number of adopted ITKs and farming experience of the farmers remained highly positive ($R^2 = 0.72$); level of education of the farmers and number of ITKs adopted remained curvilinear ($R^2 = 0.68$); whereas, size of the farm ponds fitted negatively with number of adopted ITKs ($R^2 = 0.56$). Such trend was identical in Bankura district also as positive correlations were observed between number of adopted ITKs and average annual yield ($R^2 = 0.86$);

between number of adopted ITKs and average fish farming experience ($R^2 = 0.75$); between number of ITKs adopted and level of education of the farmers ($R^2 = 0.70$); between number of ITKs adopted and size of the farm ponds ($R^2 = 0.61$); and between number of ITKs adopted and number of fish species cultured ($R^2 = 0.63$). In Purba Medinipur, such relationship in general, remained identical as correlations between number of ITKs adopted and, average annual yield remained strongly positive. Von Bertalanffy's growth model revealed higher growth coefficient (K) values of cultured fish and shrimps parallel with the number of ITKs adopted

Regarding adoption of the available ITKs, the limiting factors as perceived by the farmers were (i) ITKs have limitations and were partially effective as solution to the problems, (ii) enormous size of waterbodies that needs huge quantity of plant derivatives and much time for application, (iii) reserved mentality in sharing of technical knowledge by the elderly, experienced farmers except their descendants (iv) lack of proper knowledge on the dosage of the inputs (v) lack of published documents, (vi) lack of sufficient input materials and (vii) uncertainty and holding of the short term leased- in ponds.

Though, most of the input oriented ITKs were found to be based on sound scientific reasonings, the timing, dosage, actual requirements appeared highly variable and often arbitrary. Even, application of a particular ITK by different farmers were temporally and spatially variable because of absence of authentic scientific documents. In some cases, the application of input materials as ITKs seemed unrealistic and unscientific to some extent viz. applying fly ash and cement directly into the pond for remediation of obnoxious gases and reduce suffocation of the cultured fish. This is nothing but bypassing the real problem out of huge organic enrichment, rather, blanketing the pond bed by cementing it. By doing this, the benthic heterotrophic environment and the mineralization processes on the surface layer of the sediment is being blocked, that appeared scientifically wrong. Therefore, the hypothesis of adoption of ITKs remained unscientific in many cases; even they might be counterproductive.